

CHARACTERIZATION AND MODELING OF DAMAGE AT THE MESOSCALE OF WOVEN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

C. Fagiano^{1*}, M. Hirsekorn¹, G. Grail¹, V. Chiaruttini¹

¹ ONERA, The French Aerospace Lab, F-92322 Châtillon, France.

* Corresponding author (christian.fagiano@onera.fr)

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1 Introduction

Composite materials manufactured using textile architectures are receiving a growing interest in the field of advanced structural applications. One of the reasons is related to the fact that the microstructure of fiber preforms can be tailored to satisfy specific needs in terms of mechanical performance. Other advantages include (i) ease of handling for automation, (ii) virtual elimination of interlaminar surfaces making them less sensible to delamination effects, and (iii) the ability to be draped or directly woven in complex shapes [1]. Most textile composites are manufactured using matrix injection/infusion, or thermoforming. In order to increase the fiber volume fraction in the composite to improve its mechanical performances, the preform is usually compacted before adding the matrix. Thus, complex yarn shapes can be generated during the manufacturing process, with (i) local variations of both the section and the fiber volume fraction in the yarns [2;3], (ii) random shifts and nesting between the layers [2;4;5], and/or (iii) complex contact regions between the yarns. The shape and orientation of the yarns and their interaction have an important influence on the local strain/stress distributions of the composite under mechanical loading, as well as on damage initiation and propagation [8-10]. For instance, it has been shown in different studies that the nesting between the layers of a multilayered textile composite has to be taken into account since it can lead to different damage initiation conditions, and different patterns of damage progression [10-13]. Therefore, at the mesoscale (the scale of the smallest Representative Volume Element (RVE) describing the interlacing of warp and weft yarns), it is extremely important to

generate geometries with yarn shapes as close as possible to reality.

Several automated tools have been proposed throughout the last decade able to generate geometrical models of fabric reinforcements, and covering a huge variety of weaving patterns [14-17]. However, most of them are not able to take into account the preforming step of the fabric. Therefore, an idealized geometric model of the fabric is commonly adopted, resulting in resin rich areas that are bigger than those observed experimentally. In this case, higher fiber volume fractions than observed in reality have to be used inside the yarns (even non-physical values greater than 90%) to preserve the overall fiber volume fraction in the composite (typically between 50 and 60%). Yarn shapes closer to those of the real composite can be obtained from Finite Element (FE) modeling of the dry fabric preforming [6;19-22]. These methods are used in this work to create geometries of a slightly unbalanced four-layer plain weave fabric, compacted to different thicknesses, and with different types of nesting between the layers.

A technique frequently used to mesh meso-scale RVEs is the voxelisation [28;29]. The main advantage of this method lies in its simplicity since the meshing can be carried out in only a few operations regardless of the complexity of the geometry. However, it can provide an extremely rough and mesh-dependent representation of local stress and strain fields, especially at material interfaces, leading to bad predictions of damage onset. In this work, an algorithm recently developed at ONERA [23], able to mesh any kind of deformed preform as well as the injected matrix complement (section 2.1), is used to generate RVE meshes that are consistent at the contact zones (section 2.2). The algorithm avoids the need for introduction of

artificial matrix layers to avoid meshing problems close to the contact regions, as done for instance in [12;24-27].

As far as the modeling of damage at the mesoscale is concerned, approaches based on continuum damage mechanics have been often used to simulate the damage mechanisms [8;24;26]. The advantage of these methods is that they are based on damage variables able to predict the degraded stiffness without introducing cracks directly into the mesh, thus making the computation simpler compared to methods based on fracture mechanics. Being usually combined with well established failure criteria, continuum damage models show, in general, robust damage detection. However, when it comes to damage propagation the calculations can show non-physical behaviors [26]. In this case, damage modeling based on fracture mechanics seems to be necessary to predict the behaviour of a woven composite structure.

The purpose of this work is to present the FE tools developed at ONERA for the evaluation of the effects of mesoscale damage on the mechanical performances of a woven composite part. First, the generated RVEs are used to calculate the homogenized macroscopic elastic constants of the composite using a volumetric homogenization technique. Then, the local strain distributions obtained using meso-FE simulations are compared with those obtained experimentally using stereo digital image correlation (section 3). Finally, microscopic observations have been carried on the tested specimens to characterize the sequence of intra-yarn transverse damage. Based on these experimental observations, discrete intra-yarn transverse cracks are inserted into the yarns of the RVE, perpendicular to the loading direction (section 4). This is done using the crack insertion algorithm developed by Chiaruttini et al. [30]. The effects of mesoscale transverse damage on the macroscopic mechanical properties of the composite are evaluated et compared with the experimental data (section 5). Although the development of the method is still at an early stage, the obtained results are quite encouraging, thus confirming the applicability of the procedure for future damage analyses of woven polymer matrix composites.

2 Numerical modeling

2.1 Generation of consistent meshes

The automated method for the generation of smooth FE meshes of mesoscale RVEs is based on a first detection of the contact zones between the yarns of a preformed and compacted reinforcement [23] (see section 2.2). This is done via a parametric representation of the yarn surfaces, which may have arbitrary shapes. First, a group of lines L_{ln} following the fiber direction of the yarn, and sampled with n points P_{il} , are defined on the yarn surface. Then, at each point P_{il} a section S_i is defined that runs once around the yarn, ending at its starting point, such that the sections S_i do not cross or touch each other. Either the line or section group is chosen in such a way that the yarns (L^B to L^G on Fig. 1) in contact with a given yarn (L^A on Fig. 1) are represented by a group that is approximately perpendicular to the lines belonging to the yarn under consideration.

The proposed yarn surface representation is used to detect the contact zones between yarns. Contact points are created at the half distance between the closest points of the lines belonging to the yarns under consideration if the distance is below a certain tolerance tol . The result of this algorithm is the definition of contact zones based on the contact points assigned to the yarn surfaces. An example of contact points detected on the upper surface of a yarn is shown in Fig. 1. The color of the contact points indicates the yarn to which they are in contact. Then, the yarn surfaces are resampled such that each yarn surface contains the contact points that are assigned to it, as shown in Fig.2. This is done for all the yarns of the RVE.

The grid shown in Fig. 2 seems to allow for an immediate representation of the yarn surfaces by quadrilateral elements, by using the lines and sections as element edges. However, the four points are almost never coplanar. Therefore, each quadrilateral is divided into two triangles by taking into account the contours of the different contact zones. The generated yarn surface meshes are composed of triangles that are exactly the same in the regions of contact, and the contact points sharing the same position are finally merged. An algorithm able to create the yarn and matrix contours on the external surfaces of the unit cell was developed based on the yarn surface representation of Fig. 2. In

this way, a consistent FE mesh composed of closed surfaces is obtained, which can be filled with tetrahedrons using an automated volume meshing algorithm. The result for a compacted and nested layup of a four-layered plain weave fabric with injected matrix is shown in Fig. 3. The element size of the mesh depends on the sampling of the yarn surfaces.

2.2 Application to a multi-layer compacted and nested plain weave layup

The algorithm presented in section 2.1 is used to generate a consistent FE mesh of a nested and compacted RVE of a four-layered composite with the matrix complement injected by resin transfer molding (RTM). In the real composite, the fabric layers are shifted randomly with respect to each other due to the manufacturing process. From the same architecture different weaving patterns of the fabric can be extrapolated, as shown in Fig. 4. For a single ply these patterns are strictly equivalent if periodic boundary conditions are applied in the plane of the fabric.

Three different RVEs were generated for this work. In the first one, A-type weaving patterns are stacked on top of each other without generation of nesting between the layers. In the second one, A-type and B-type weaving patterns are stacked alternately to produce maximum nesting [5] between the layers. This RVE is shown Fig. 5. In the third one, four random-type weaving patterns are stacked to generate a random shifting between the layers. The compaction of the dry fabric during the performing step in the mold is simulated using FE modeling (ABAQUS), and a Coulomb friction law is assumed between the yarns in contact. The adopted procedure is the same as in [20;21] with a simplified mechanical behaviour for the yarns [20], which in the case of compaction yields qualitatively good yarn shapes. Fig. 5 shows the result of the performing step on a four-layered plain weave RVE having maximum nesting, compacted from an initial thickness of 2.9 [mm] to a final thickness of 1.6 [mm]. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to the yarn extremities. The local yarn orientations are obtained by projection of the yarn center line, and assigned to each integration point.

The compacted geometry is then meshed using the procedure presented in section 2.1, to obtain the RVE shown in Fig. 3. The yarn volume fraction of

the RVE (total volume occupied by the yarns divided by the total volume of the unit cell) is 52.0% in the non-compacted state and 87.3% in the compacted one. Therefore, in order to obtain a total fiber volume fraction in the composite of 60% (a typical value for compacted fabrics), the fiber volume fraction in the yarns would have to reach an unphysical value of 115% if a non-compacted geometry is used, as done in [10;12;24;28]. The same problem was encountered by Ivanov et al. [18], for braided fabrics. If a compacted unit cell is used, as the one shown in Fig. 3, the fiber volume fraction in the yarns has to be 68.7% in order to reach 60% of total fiber volume fraction in the composite, which is quite a realistic value.

The RVEs used in section 4 and 5 to evaluate (i) the homogenized macroscopic elastic constants of the composite, (ii) the local strain distributions, and (iii) the effects of mesoscale transverse damage on the macroscopic mechanical properties of the composite, were obtained using the proposed procedure. Grail's algorithm [23] is used to generate the FE mesh for both the fabric and the matrix complement. Periodic BCs can easily be applied since opposite external surfaces of the mesh are perfectly equivalent. In this study, periodic boundary conditions are applied in the plane of the fabric only, whereas the top and bottom surfaces are free. Isotropic elastic behaviour is adopted for the matrix and transverse isotropic elastic behaviour for the yarns. The yarn properties are determined by means of micromechanical analyses, as done by Melro et al. in [24]. The aim of the microscale modeling and homogenization is the calculation of the elastic and strength parameters of a representative volume element at the microscale to obtain a linear-elastic behaviour law for the homogenized yarn applicable at the mesoscale. The fiber orientation at each integration point is obtained by projection of the yarn center line extracted from the compaction modeling.

3 Experimental analyses

Experimental tests were carried out at ONERA for different four-layer plain weave fabric composites under uni-axial static tensile load to (i) determine the local strain distributions in the plies and (ii) characterize the onset and patterns of progressive damage mechanisms. Plain fabric architecture was chosen because it is the smallest pattern commonly

used, which simplifies the comparison between experimental analyses and numerical simulations. The properties of the plain fiberglass fabric used in the experimental tests are reported in Tab. 1. The fibers are made of E-Glass fibers. The epoxy matrix is the Araldite LY564 produced by Huntsman. Different specimens have been tested under different kind of loadings, e.g. monotonic and incremental loadings. An example of incremental loading applied during the experimental tests is shown in Fig. 6. In contrast to unidirectional composites, the yarn interlacing pattern in textile composites causes heterogeneous strain fields with large strain gradients around the yarn crimp regions. Therefore, classical electrical resistance strain gauges do not provide an adequate spatial resolution and only a full-field strain measuring technique with high spatial resolution and strain sensitivity can be applied to determine local strain profiles. For this reason, the local strains on the composite surface have been measured using stereo digital image correlation, as done, e.g., in [32].

These distributions are compared in section 5 with the results obtained from meso-FE simulations. In order to understand the local damage behaviour, both acoustic emission and microscopic analyses have been used. This instrumentation allows for detecting the damage initiation locations in the composite and its propagation. Moreover, microscopic observation of the tested composite laminates gives information on the sequence of intra-yarn transverse damage occurrence (perpendicular to the load direction), and the subsequent interface debonding between the yarns, at different locations in the laminate, starting from crack initiation to the final failure of the composite [8]. For all the tested specimens, the number of visible cracks transverse to the loading direction (ρ_s = number of cracks/mm²) and the total length λ_s (mm/mm²) were measured. In case of specimens subjected to incremental loadings, ρ_s and λ_s are calculated at each loading step, as shown in Fig. 6 for a specimen subjected to 9 steps of applied stress in the weft direction before failure. A microscopic analysis has been performed on the same specimen to characterize the damage phenomena. The damage observed just before failure is shown in Fig. 7 (this image was not taken at the failure location). Intra-yarn transverse cracking is observed due to the

coalescence of micro-decohesions between fibers and matrix, whereas matrix cracking at the meso-scale is not detected. However, plastic zones are detected (see Fig. 7) at the crack tips, indicating that non-linear behaviours, i.e. viscoplasticity, should be taken into account in the mechanical modeling of the matrix.

4 Discrete damage modeling

In the proposed procedure, discrete damage in the form of cracks is introduced in the RVE. Thus, the influence of damage on the local stress state can be directly observed. Moreover, this method allows the introduction of damage in the RVE as it is observed on the real specimen since the cracks can be counted, measured and localized on the composite. In this paper the attention is restricted to the modeling of intra-yarn transverse cracking, and inter-yarn micro decohesion at the crack's tips. Transverse cracks are generated by the coalescence of micro-decohesions between fibers and matrix due to transverse loading, as shown in Fig. 7 for a specimen composed of E-Glass fibers and epoxy matrix LY564. These cracks never cut the fibers. The crack front can be represented using planes cutting the yarn, as shown in Fig. 8. The cracks are inserted using the algorithm developed by Chiaruttini et al. [30]. This algorithm allows the simulation of complex crack growth phenomena, and one of the advantages of this approach is that almost any kind of cracks can be introduced in very complex meshes. It is based on the modification of an initial undamaged finite element mesh that is refined in the vicinity of the crack front. The first stage of the procedure is the design of a suitable geometry that represents the surface of the crack itself. This geometry is represented by a surface mesh made of linear triangular elements. In this work, the cracks are supposed to be perpendicular to the loading direction. In the second stage of the procedure the volume mesh of the uncracked structure is adapted to the crack geometry. A volume remeshing operation is then applied to the complete mesh. Zones of micro-decohesion are automatically generated around the crack tips, as shown in Fig. 9. These zones depend on the element size close to the crack tips. It is important to remark that only the yarns are cut and not the matrix complement. Special treatments are also performed on element

faces during the procedure to cope with the crack front intersection and some topological difficulties that could arise for highly curved cracks. The obtained mesh is finally rebuilt using an adaptive remeshing strategy to eliminate bad quality elements and to provide a suitable discretization for accurate finite element solution and stress intensity factors computation. This approach has been implemented in the Z-Set (ZéBulon) finite element software co-developed by the École des Mines de Paris, NW Numerics and Onera.

5 Results

The purpose of this section is to show the capacity of the proposed finite element procedure to evaluate the effects of mesoscopic damage on the macroscopic mechanical properties of the material. The first part of the analysis concerns linear meso-FE simulations to calculate the macroscopic elastic constants of the undamaged material by periodic homogenization. This part also allows the analyses of the influence of nesting on the macroscopic in-plane elastic moduli of the RVE, and the analysis of the internal stress/strain fields of the material under load. The mechanical properties of the fibers (E-Glass) are: $E_f = 72.4$ [GPa], $\nu_f = 0.2$. The properties of the Araldite LY564 matrix provided by the manufacturer are: $E_m = 3.2$ [GPa], $\nu_m = 0.35$. The fiber volume fraction of the composite estimated experimentally is 47%. The unit cell dimensions of the fabric on the warp and weft directions are, respectively, 9.12 mm et 10 mm, and its thickness is 1.65 mm. At the mesoscopic scale the behaviour of the RVE is orthotropic, with the three directions of orthotropy corresponding to the warp, weft, and thickness directions. The FE software ZéBulon was used for the simulations. Three RVEs were generated and analyzed, as explained in section 2.2. The FE meshes are composed of quadratic tetrahedral elements with standard full integration. The elastic moduli of the yarns, calculated by micromechanical analyses as explained in section 2.2, are shown in Tab. 2, where T_f is the fiber volume fraction used at the microscale, L is the fiber direction, and T is the direction transverse to the fibers. The fiber volume fraction T_f of the yarns provides a global fiber volume fraction in the RVE of 47%. The homogenized macroscopic elastic constants of each RVE are calculated using a

volumetric homogenization technique. The results are shown in Tab. 3, where the index "1" represents the weft direction, and the index "2" represents the warp direction. The elastic properties obtained (i) numerically by taking into account different types of nesting between the layers, (ii) analytically using the Mori-Tanaka method (MT) adapted to woven composite materials [32], and (iii) by means of the experimental analyses presented in section 3, are shown in Tab. 3. All the results are quite close, meaning that the influence of nesting on the homogenized macroscopic elastic constants is negligible.

The strain distributions obtained numerically are shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, respectively for the deformations ε_{11} (loading direction) and ε_{22} . The strain patterns obtained considering (a) random, (b) maximal, and (c) no nesting between the plies are quite different, meaning that the real nesting between the layers has to be taken into account in the study of damage onset and propagation, as concluded by Grail in [23]. This is due to the fact that the strains are concentrated mainly on the resin rich areas of the composite. These zones depend on the assumed nesting between the layers. The strain distributions obtained by stereo digital image correlation are also reported in Fig. 10d and Fig. 11d. The RVE with random nesting between the layers yield the strain fields that are closest to the experimental results.

Discrete damage was introduced in the RVE with random distribution between the layers in order to be as close as possible to the data obtained experimentally. Transverse damage was introduced in the RVE based on the fracture surfaces observed experimentally. The number of cracks inserted in the RVE are based on the number of visible cracks transverse to the loading direction ($\rho_s =$ number of cracks/mm²) observed by means of microscopic observations, and the damage locations are chosen progressively based on the regions of maximum strain. The inserted cracks are supposed to cross instantaneously the complete RVE as for conventional multilayered composite laminates. However, for woven composite materials the cracks can stop anywhere due to the more complex geometry of the preform. This information can be obtained experimentally using computed tomography. However, this technique was not

available during the experimental analyses carried out for this work. The evolution of the elastic moduli as function of the crack density ρ_s have been investigated both numerically and experimentally, and the results for the elastic modulus E_{11} are shown in Fig. 12. The elastic moduli were calculated for each loading step by means of linear regression on the elastic regions of the stress/strain curve. A virtual gauge composed of four adjacent RVEs was used to calculate the average strains measured by stereo digital image correlation. The experimental results show small oscillations in the trends of the elastic moduli as function of crack density, as shown in Fig. 12 for the elastic modulus E_{11} . A virtual gauge composed of a larger number of RUCs was also adopted on the stereo digital image correlation data to control whether these oscillations are concentrated locally. These additional analyses confirmed the first trend of data, meaning that these oscillations concern the entire surface of the specimen. The numerical results are in good agreement with the experiments. However, the numerically calculated curves are more regular than the experimental ones. This confirms that the proposed tools are promising for the prediction of damage effects on the macro-mechanical properties of woven composite structures. For the sake of clarity, the average strains of the stress-strain curve associated to the behavior shown in Fig. 12 are calculated by means of a virtual gauge covering an area of the specimen that did not reach failure. In areas where failure is reached, (i) interface debonding between the yarns, (ii) longitudinal intra-yarn cracking, and finally (iii) fiber failure have to be taken into account in the discrete damage modeling of the RVE.

6 Conclusions

The method presented in this work allows for automated generation of consistent FE meshes of meso-scale composite unit cells with deformed, compacted, and nested textile reinforcements. The multiple complex contact zones between yarns are correctly described and meshed consistently without the need for inserting an artificial matrix layer between the yarns. The yarn surface representation is smooth, allowing for an accurate prediction of the stress distribution, which is crucial for the modeling

of damage onset and evolution. The procedure was illustrated for different four-layered plain weave fabric composites under elementary loadings on the plane of the fabric. The obtained deformation fields were compared qualitatively with the strain fields obtained experimentally by stereo digital image correlation. The strain fields calculated by means of meso-FE analyses are in good agreement with the experimental data only if random-type weaving patterns are stacked to generate random shifts between the layers of the RVE. The macroscopic elastic constants calculated numerically by means of volumetric homogenization were also evaluated. All RVEs provide results that are in good agreement with the experimental data. Hence, the nesting between the layers seems to have a negligible influence on the calculation of the elastic properties of the material. Furthermore, effects of mesoscopic damage on the macroscopic elastic properties of a RVE with random nesting have been analyzed. The results were also compared with available experimental data. The module loss in the direction of the loading due to intra-yarn transverse cracking was analyzed in detail. The developed tools provide trends that are quite similar to those obtained experimentally. Future improvements of discrete damage modeling in woven composite RVEs will take into account interface debonding between the yarns, intra-yarn longitudinal cracking, and fiber breaking to provide appropriate predictions of the structural behavior until failure.

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Figures

Fig. 1. Yarn surfaces represented using a group of lines L and sections S, with detection of the contact zones between the yarns.

Fig. 2. Resampled yarn surface with contact zones.

Fig. 3. FE mesh of a nested and compacted RVE of a four-layered plain weave fabric with half of the injected matrix visualized.

Fig. 4. Representations of the different weaving patterns that can be extrapolated from the same weave architecture.

Fig. 5. FE simulation of the compaction during the preforming step of 4 layers of plain weave fabric with out-of-phase stacking.

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Fig. 6. Example of incremental loading applied in the weft direction of a specimen during the experimental tests.

Fig. 7. Damage observed on a specimen subjected to incremental loading on the weft direction of the composite.

Fig. 8. Cutting planes representing the crack fronts inside the RVE (only the yarns are cut).

Fig. 9. Decohesion zones around the crack's tips.

Fig. 10: Strain field ϵ_{11} obtained on the upper surface of four adjacent RVEs subjected to a traction load on the weft direction ($\sigma_{11} = 90$ MPa): nesting (a) random, (b) maximal, and (c) zero. These fields are compared with the strain distributions obtained by means of the stereo digital image correlation technique (d).

Fig. 11: Strain field ε_{22} obtained on the upper surface of four adjacent RVEs subjected to a traction load on the weft direction ($\sigma_{11} = 90$ MPa): nesting (a) random, (b) maximal, and (c) zero. These fields are compared with the strain distributions obtained by means of the stereo digital image correlation technique (d).

Fig. 12: Experimental and numerical investigation of the effect of transverse damage on the module E_{11} as function of the crack density ρ_s .

Paramètres	Unité	Valeurs
Densité linéaire des torons	Tex	1200
Contexture	chaînes.cm ⁻¹ trames.cm ⁻¹	2.2x2
Masse surfacique	g.m ⁻²	504

Tab. 1. Properties of the plain fiberglass fabric used for the experimental tests.

Nesting	T _f on the yarns (%)	E _L (GPa)	E _T (GPa)	G _{LT} (GPa)	v _{LT}	v _{TT}
zero	62.24	45.94	11.94	8.67	0.309	0.397
max	56.92	42.30	10.28	7.56	0.318	0.418
random	56.88	42.15	10.23	7.52	0.318	0.419

Tab. 2: Elastic properties calculated for the yarns of the different RVEs based on the nesting between the yarns.

Method	Nesting	E ₁₁ (GPa)	E ₂₂ (GPa)	G ₁₂ (GPa)	v ₁₂	v ₂₃
EF	zero	21.5	22.7	6.63	0.14	0.40
EF	max	21.3	22.6	6.60	0.14	0.41
EF	random	20.9	22.4	6.47	0.13	0.41
MT	random	21.2	22.6	6.46	0.12	0.42
Tests	/	21.04	x	x	0.13	x

Tab. 3: Macroscopic elastic properties of the four-layer plain architecture obtained (i) numerically (EF) by taking into account different types of nesting between the layers, (ii) analytically (MT) [32] et (iii) experimentally.